

NUMERICAL DAMAGE STUDY OF TWIN-CROSSED SPIRAL- CONFINED CONCRETE UNDER COMPRESSION

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ABSTRACT: *This study investigates numerically the influence of twin-crossed spiral reinforcement on the damage compressive behaviour of high-performance concrete columns. Three reinforcement configurations are analysed: single spiral, crossed spirals, and twin-crossed spirals. Finite element simulations are performed using the RICRAG damage model implemented in the CAST3M code. Compared with single spirals, the results show that twin-crossed spiral reinforcement significantly improves confinement efficiency, load-carrying capacity, and ductility. Redistribution of internal forces within the spirals was also observed simultaneously with the evolution of reinforcement plasticity and concrete damage, leading to amplified internal forces at mid-height of spirals.*

KEYWORDS: *High performance concrete, Twin-crossed spiral, Axial compression behaviour, Damage mechanics, Redistribution of internal forces.*

1 INTRODUCTION

Enhancing the mechanical performance of reinforced concrete using spiral reinforcement remains a significant challenge in structural engineering. Among the emerging reinforcement strategies, crossed spiral reinforcements in columns have attracted growing interest due to their potential to improve concrete confinement and enhance both strength and ductility. This study investigates numerically the effect of incorporating either two or four crossed spiral reinforcements on the structural behaviour of confined concrete columns. By using the *Cast3M Finite Element Analysis code* developed by the CEA in France, the analysis is performed within the framework of continuous damage mechanics. For this purpose, the (Richard *et al.*, 2010) damage model is employed and integrated with a non-local theoretical approach (Giry, Dufour and Mazars, 2011) to achieve a more accurate representation of progressive degradation and failure mechanisms. Moreover, the configuration with two crossed spirals offers the advantage, over a single spiral, of doubling the spacing for equivalent volumetric confinement ratios as defined in Section 21.6 of the ACI CODE-318-19. However, adopting the same pitch in both arrangements results, in the case of crossed spirals, in a doubled volumetric ratio and, consequently, a denser reinforcement layout. Such reinforcement congestion is frequently

observed in critical zones, such as column ends, where the reduced spiral spacing restricts concrete placement. This limitation is particularly significant in the case of normal-strength concrete, when the maximum aggregate size exceeds the available spacing, which constitutes a notable drawback. The configuration with four crossed spirals creates reinforcement zones of even higher density, with further reduced spiral spacing. To ensure proper concrete flow, it is therefore necessary to limit the maximum aggregate size in accordance with the minimum spacing between spirals resulting from these crossings. This maximum size typically does not exceed 10 mm. For this reason, the present study is restricted to the use of high-performance concrete formulated with a reduced maximum aggregate size, enabling not only enhanced mechanical strength but also improved workability. This limitation also allows the results obtained herein to be compared directly with those reported experimentally by (Marvel *et al.*, 2014) and numerically by (Al-Osta *et al.*, 2018).

The existing literature in this field remains relatively limited. In the context of pure axial compression, (Ibrahim, Al-osta and Hindi, 2015) employed the continuous damage plasticity (CDP) model (Lee and Fenves, 1998) as implemented in (*Abaqus Software*) to generate stress-strain curves that correlated well with the experimental results of

(Marvel *et al.*, 2014). (Al-Osta *et al.*, 2018) later extended the numerical study using the same damage model to explore key parameters, including spiral spacing (S), the core-to-section diameter ratio (γ), and concrete compressive strength. Their results revealed that increasing γ enhances ultimate load capacity without affecting ductility. Experimentally, (Hindi, Al-Qattawi and Elsharief, 2012) and (Marvel *et al.*, 2014) examined circular columns confined with a single spiral and with two crossed spirals. For equivalent volumetric confinement ratios, achieved by doubling the pitch spacing ($2S$) in crossed spirals versus simple spacing (S) in regular spirals, both configurations showed comparable strengths and similar or slightly improved ductility. Moreover, when the volumetric ratio was doubled for crossed spirals at the same pitch (S), (Marvel *et al.*, 2014) reported significant increases in strength and ductility. In addition, these crossed spirals fail at different times, thereby delaying the loss of load-bearing capacity and increasing energy dissipation. Other studies performed by (Chen, Feng and Yin, 2012) have introduced multi-spiral reinforcement systems for rectangular and circular columns, demonstrating superior confinement effects and enhanced strength and ductility compared to traditional stirrups. Furthermore, (Havlásek, Jirásek and Bittnar, 2019) proposed an innovative finite element framework using a new CDP (Grassl *et al.*, 2013) model to optimise multi-spiral layouts, reducing experimental efforts while maintaining accurate predictions of confined concrete behaviour. (Wang *et al.*, 2020) further proposed a simplified finite-element approach for predicting the axial compression behaviour of rectangular columns with interlocking multispiral systems.

For the combined compression and flexural loading case, (Hindi and Turechek, 2008) and (Hindi, 2013) have experimentally reported, for spiral-confined columns, distinct failure modes under constant axial load and reversed cyclic lateral displacements. Unlike conventional single spirals, which experienced premature ruptures, crossed spirals remained intact throughout the loading process. In the presence of crossed spirals, the columns predominantly failed due to buckling or fracture of longitudinal reinforcement bars. Moreover, columns reinforced with crossed spirals exhibited a significantly enhanced ductility. Similarly, (Havaei and Keramati, 2015) experimentally investigated the effects of two critical parameters: the steel grade and the volumetric ratios of the crossed spirals, highlighting their influence on the structural performance under seismic loading. Other experimental works by (Ou *et al.*, 2015) proposed innovative spiral reinforcement schemes

for large columns, demonstrating superior ductility and energy dissipation under seismic loading even with reduced transverse reinforcement.

For the combined flexural and torsional loading, numerical studies appear to be also much less abundant. To our knowledge, only simple spirals have been investigated, as in the work of (Belarbi, Prakash and You, 2009) who analysed confined circular reinforced concrete bridge columns. On the experimental side, (Browning, Marvel and Hindi, 2007) reported that columns with a single spiral exhibit an inherently asymmetric strength under reversed cyclic torsional loading, with higher resistance in one direction of rotation. In contrast, columns reinforced with crossed spirals demonstrated a more favourable behaviour. The two spirals tend to fail sequentially, allowing the second spiral to maintain partial confinement after the first has failed. This mechanism contributes to a significantly improved ductility and residual capacity of crossed-spiral columns under severe loading conditions.

To address the objectives outlined above, the structure of this paper is organised as follows. Section 2 offers a concise overview of the adopted RICRAG damage model as described by (Richard *et al.*, 2010) employed in the numerical simulations of this study. Section 3 presents the numerical investigations, encompassing elastic, plastic, and damage-based analyses, along with a detailed interpretation of the results. Section 4 provides the concluding remarks and outlines perspectives for future research.

2 BRIEF OVERVIEW OF THE RICRAG DAMAGE MODEL

Formulated within the framework of thermodynamics for irreversible processes, the RICRAG damage model developed by (Richard *et al.*, 2010) provides a framework for predicting the failure behaviour of concrete and other quasi-brittle materials. In the isotropic damage formulation, which constitutes the focus of this study, each point in the structure is associated with a scalar internal damage variable d which belongs to the interval $[0,1]$, representing the progressive degradation of stiffness due to material deterioration.

$$\sigma = (1 - d)\mathbf{H}\varepsilon \quad (1)$$

Where σ , ε , and \mathbf{H} denote the Cauchy stress tensor, small strain tensor, and the fourth-order Hooke elasticity tensor, respectively. Here, $d = 0$ corresponds to an undamaged state, while $d = 1$ indicates complete material failure. The damage variable d depends on a state variable Y , which represents the local energy release rate and is a function of strain:

$$Y = Y(\varepsilon) \quad (2)$$

To mitigate strain localisation issues and enhance numerical stability, a non-local regularisation strategy is introduced (Giry, Dufour and Mazars, 2011). This involves averaging the state variable Y over a characteristic neighbourhood of each point, leading to a non-local variable Y^{nl} , as defined by:

$$Y^{nl}(x) = \frac{\int_{\Omega(x)} W(x-s) Y(s) ds}{\int_{\Omega(x)} W(x-s) ds} \quad (3)$$

Here, $W(x-s)$ is a weighting function or typically a Gaussian distribution which governing the influence relation of point located with x and neighbouring points located with s within the domain $\Omega(x)$:

$$W(x-s) = \exp\left[-\left(\frac{2\|x-s\|}{l_c \cdot \rho(\mathbf{x}, \sigma_{prin}(s))}\right)^2\right] \quad (4)$$

Where l_c is a characteristic length and $\rho(\mathbf{x}, \sigma_{prin}(s))$ captures stress-state dependent interactions. It depends on the point location x and $\sigma_{prin}(s)$ the principal stress state on the surrounding point s .

Consequently, the damage evolution law is defined in terms of:

$$\dot{d} = d(Y^{nl}) \quad (5)$$

Noting that the damage starts above a threshold Y_0 ($d = 0$ for $Y^{nl} \leq Y_0$) and cannot decrease seeing that ($\dot{d} \geq 0$).

The RICRAG model also incorporates additional features to represent complex concrete behaviour, including elasticity-damage coupling, sliding with friction across crack surfaces, and both isotropic and kinematic hardening such as the expression of the damage variable can be written:

$$d = 1 - \frac{1}{1 + \left(A_{Dir} H((\varepsilon_{ij})_+ (\sigma_{ij})_+) + A_{Ind} (1 - H((\varepsilon_{ij})_+ (\sigma_{ij})_+)) \right) (Y^{nl} - Y_0)} \quad (6)$$

A_{Dir} and A_{Ind} are the material parameters which can be interpreted as brittleness terms, respectively, in tension and in compression. H is the Heaviside function. The symbol $\langle \cdot \rangle_+$ denotes the positive part of the tensor. More details about this model can be found in (Richard *et al.*, 2010)

3 NUMERICAL ANALYSIS

3.1 Studied problem

To ensure direct comparison with available studies in the literature, the present work adopts the same parameters as those reported by (Marvel *et al.*, 2014) and (Al-Osta *et al.*, 2018). The study analyses the elastoplastic damage behaviour of circular high-performance concrete columns, each 1 m in height and 350 mm in diameter, numerically tested under axial compression. The reinforcement consists of ten longitudinal steel bars of 16 mm diameter with a 50 mm concrete cover. To address the research

objective, the concrete is confined by steel spirals arranged in three configurations, as illustrated in figures 1 and 2: 1S (single spiral), X (two crossed spirals), and XX (four crossed spirals). To prevent damage localisation at the column extremities, two different spiral pitches are adopted. Specifically, the pitch at mid-height, denoted S_m , is set to twice the pitch at the extremities, denoted S_e , such that $S_m = 2S_e$. In this study, three column types are considered, designated as 50S10, 50X10, and 50XX10. These correspond to a mid-height pitch $S_m = 50$ mm extending over a 500 mm central zone (half the column height), and an end pitch $S_e = 25$ mm applied over each extremity for a length of 250 mm (a quarter of the total column height).

Fig 1 Three-dimensional view longitudinal front view of the 1S, X, and XX configurations.

Fig 2 Mesh representation of spiral confinement configurations (1S, X, and XX) with concrete

Table 1. Geometric and Mechanical Characteristics of Concrete and Steel.

ϕ_{sp} (mm)	f_{yh} (MPa)	f_{c28} (MPa)	E_s (MPa)	ν_s	ν_c
10	448.9	63.2	198836.6	0.3	0.18

The geometric and mechanical parameters including the spiral bar diameter ϕ_{sp} , the Young's

moduli of steel E_s , the Poisson’s ratios for concrete and steel ν_c and ν_s , respectively, the compressive strength of concrete at 28 days f_{c28} and the yield strength of the spiral reinforcement f_{yh} , are summarised in Table 1. It is worth noting that the constitutive model adopted for the steel incorporates an elastoplastic response with isotropic hardening as depicted by the stress–strain relationship depicted in figure 3.

Fig 3 Stress–Strain curve of the reinforcing Steel used.

The material properties adopted for the RICRAG model include the tensile strength F_t , tensile brittleness A_{Dir} , compressive brittleness A_{Ind} , and the first γ_1 and second α_0 kinematic hardening moduli. These parameters are presented in Table 2.

Table 2. RICRAG damage parameters

Parameters	Values
F_t	3.23×10^6 Pa
A_{Dir}	$2.85 \times 10^{-2} \text{J}^{-1} \text{m}^3$
A_{Ind}	$3.25 \times 10^{-5} \text{J}^{-1} \text{m}^3$
γ_1	7×10^9 Pa
α_0	$0.28 \times 10^{-7} \text{Pa}^{-1}$

The values in Table 2 were chosen to ensure that the stress–strain curve obtained with the RICRAG model in CAST3M closely matches the experimental curve for the 50X10 configuration reported by (Marvel *et al.*, 2014), as illustrated in Figure 4. For comparison, Figure 4 also includes the curve obtained by (Al-Osta *et al.*, 2018) using the CDP model in Abaqus for the same configuration. The three curves show close agreement, with peak stresses of approximately 100 MPa occurring at strain levels of 0.05 %, 0.09 %, and 1 %, respectively.

Fig 4 Comparison of RICRAG, Experimental, and CDP Model predictions

3.2 Finite element model description

As mentioned in the introduction, the finite element models were developed to investigate the mechanical behaviour of high-performance concrete (HPC) columns confined with spiral reinforcement in the three configurations described previously. Numerical simulations were conducted using the CAST3M finite element software. The three-dimensional meshes were generated with linear elements, comprising 10480, 10930, and 11830 elements for the 1S, X, and XX configurations, respectively. The concrete domain was discretised into 9600 elements, including 8400 hexahedral eight-node elements (CUB8) and 1200 pentahedral six-node elements (PRI6). The longitudinal and spiral reinforcements were discretised using two-nodes, three-dimensional bar elements (SEG2), enabling precise modelling of their geometries and mechanical contributions. Each spiral consisted of 450 SEG2 elements, while the longitudinal reinforcement was discretised into 430 SEG2 elements.

Material nonlinearity was incorporated for both concrete and steel. The concrete behaviour was defined using the RICRAG damage constitutive model as presented in the previous section 2. The elastoplastic behaviour with isotropic hardening adopted for the steel, as illustrated by the stress–strain relationship in figure 3, was implemented in the CAST3M finite element code. It is noteworthy that the present study appears to be the first to explicitly incorporate steel hardening in the numerical simulation of confined concrete, thereby emphasising the novelty of the proposed approach. In contrast, most existing numerical models in the literature consider steel as perfectly elastoplastic, without accounting for hardening effects.

Moreover, appropriate contact conditions were defined to accurately simulate the interaction

between the concrete and the reinforcement. Specifically, bonding relationships were established along the three translational degrees of freedom for each node, linking the nodes of the concrete mesh to those of the reinforcement. These were implemented using the RELA ACCRO operator available in the CAST3M software. The ACCRO option constructs the stiffness matrix associated with the attachment of the concrete mesh to the reinforcement mesh, which includes both the spirals and the longitudinal bars. Any reinforcement point located within a concrete element is constrained to follow a linear combination of the displacements of the element's nodes. An optional floating-point parameter allows nodes situated slightly outside the boundary of the concrete element to be included in the bonding process. By default, a value of 1.e-5 is adopted.

The boundary conditions were defined by fully restraining all translational displacements of the nodes located at the base of the column, including those associated with the reinforcement. Additionally, the nodes lying along the longitudinal axis of the column were constrained horizontally in both the X and Y directions. The loading was applied incrementally under displacement-controlled conditions.

3.3 Elastic analysis

The elastic response phase corresponds to the initial stage preceding steel yielding and the initiation of concrete damage. A detailed analysis of the stress and strain field distributions offers critical insights into the structural mechanics of confined concrete, highlighting the role and interaction of the concrete and spiral confinement in governing the overall behaviour.

Fig5 Confining forces applied by spirals in the three configurations (1S, X, and XX).

Figure 5 above illustrates that, for the three configurations, the nodal reaction forces resulting

from the bonding relationships and exerted by the spirals on the concrete are not only radial in direction but also convergent in sense, i.e., oriented towards the interior of the concrete core. This observation confirms the confining effect of the spirals during the elastic phase.

Fig 6 Tensile forces in spirals for the 1S, X, and XX confinement configurations.

Figure 6 illustrates the internal tensile forces within the spirals for the three confinement configurations (1S, X, and XX). These tensile forces are significantly higher at the extremities, where the spiral spacing is reduced by half, compared to the mid-height region. The intensities range from 16 to 24 KN for the 1S case, 16 to 23 KN for the X case, and 15 to 22 KN for the XX case.

Fig 7 Elastic distribution of the normal forces intensities within spirals under 1S, X and XX cases.

Figure 7 shows more precisely the elastic distribution of these normal force intensities, represented along the curvilinear abscissa of the spirals. Across all confinement cases, tensile forces are substantially higher at the extremities compared to the mid-height region. This is directly linked to the reduced spiral pitch in these zones, which is halved relative to the central zone. Such a distribution highlights the critical role of variable pitch in improving confinement effectiveness at the column ends. In addition, increasing the quantity of spiral reinforcement results in a notable reduction in the

internal efforts in the spirals. This observation reveals an inversely proportional relationship between the density of spiral reinforcement and the induced tensile forces.

Fig 8 Elastic distribution of nodal confinement forces in 1S, X, and XX configurations.

Similar to the distribution of internal tensile forces, the confinement forces, in figure 8, are lower at the mid-height of the column than at the extremities. It is also observed that increasing the number of spirals leads to a reduction in the confinement force exerted by each individual spiral. However, due to the higher number of spirals employed, this does not imply a reduced degree of confinement for the concrete. On the contrary, the results related to the initiation and distribution of concrete damage, as presented in the following sections, clearly demonstrate an enhancement of the confinement effect. Moreover, according to figure 9, the average reduction in confinement forces per spiral in the XX configuration is 12 % at the extremities and 5 % at mid-height. In the X configuration, the corresponding reduction is 6 % at the extremities and 2 % at the mid-height of the column.

Fig 9 Reduction in Elastic Confinement Forces in X and XX Spirals Relative to 1S case.

3.4 Damage and plastic analysis

Using the same number of longitudinal bars (ten) and identical spiral pitch (50 mm) at mid-height, figure 10 presents the normal stress–strain curves obtained with the RICRAG model for the three configurations: 50S10 (single spiral), 50X10 (two crossed spirals), and 50XX10 (four crossed spirals). In the initial phase, prior to reaching their peak values, the three curves are almost identical, showing nearly overlapping responses. Notably, for a comparable level of ductility achieved across the three configurations, significant differences are observed both in the peak stress values and in the post-peak behaviour. Specifically, the configuration with four crossed spirals (50XX10) exhibits an improvement in load-carrying capacity of 5.87% compared to the two-crossed spiral case (50X10), which itself shows an enhancement of approximately 2%.

Fig10 Axial stress–strain curves for 1S, X, and XX spiral configurations using the RICRAG model.

To enable comparison with the results available in the literature, currently limited to those reported by (Al-Osta *et al.*, 2018), the present numerical investigations initially focused on the two-crossed-spiral configuration 50X10 examined in their study. Consequently, the following analysis first focuses on the distributions of damage fields in the concrete and their evolution under loading. We then examine the redistribution of internal forces within the spirals and the corresponding confinement forces they exert on the concrete core as damage progresses. For this purpose, the results in figure 11 show the damage field distributions predicted by the RICRAG model and their progression along the half-column section, defined by a longitudinal vertical cut. To more clearly illustrate the confinement forces generated by the two crossed spirals in the 50X10 configuration, each damage map is accompanied by the forces exerted by only one spiral. The damage distribution maps shown in Figure 11 were obtained under incremental loading, with imposed displacements applied to the top of the column. Specifically, the

figure depicts maps corresponding to imposed compressive displacements of 1 mm, 7 mm, 14 mm, and 33 mm, which correspond to nominal longitudinal strains of 0.1 %, 0.7 %, 1.4 %, and 3.3 %, respectively.

Fig 11 Nodal confinement forces and damage maps for longitudinal strains of 0.1%, 0.7%, 1.4 and 3.3%.

Figure 11 also shows that damage initiation occurs at mid-height of the column, specifically within the concrete cover zone. As the loading increases, the damage propagates in two directions: horizontally towards the core and vertically towards the column extremities. Distinct arc-shaped boundaries can be observed between the damaged and undamaged regions. It is worth noting that the damage progression provided by the present RICRAG model, differs from that reported by (Al-Osta et al, 2018), who, using the Abaqus software with the Concrete Damaged Plasticity (CDP) model, observed damage propagation at mid-height along an inclined plane at approximately 45 degrees to the horizontal. This difference arises from the modelling approach adopted by each model.

Additionally, a redistribution of the confinement force intensities exerted by the spirals on the core is also observed in this figure 11 as damage progresses within the column. This is further confirmed by the curves presented in figure 12, which illustrate the evolution of these confinement forces with increasing load. It is evident that initially uniform distributions observed for low imposed strain values not exceeding 0.5% gradually evolve into non-uniform bell-shaped distributions, with the peaks located at mid-height of the spirals. It is also noteworthy that these redistributions are accompanied by a progressive amplification of confinement force magnitudes as the load increases. Similarly, Figure 13 presents the redistribution of tensile forces in the spirals, in agreement with the confinement force behaviour reported in figure 12.

Fig 12 Distribution of spiral confinement forces in the 50X10 case under various longitudinal strains.

Fig 13 Distribution of spiral normal forces in the 50X10 column under various longitudinal strains.

Furthermore, for the three configurations 50S10, 50X10, and 50XX10 subjected to the same longitudinal compressive strain of 3.3% imposed at the column top, the resulting total tensile strains in the spirals are presented in Figure 14. These reach maximum values, located at mid-height, averaging around 5.25% for all three cases. The corresponding plastic strains in the spirals, presented in figure 15 for the same imposed strain of 3.3%, are also maximal at mid-height, with average values of approximately 4.64%. It is observed that the XX configuration exhibits relatively higher total and plastic strain values compared to the S and X configurations. This suggests comparable levels of deformation capacity and ductility across the three configurations. This observation is further supported by the stress–strain curves shown in figure 16, obtained under displacement-controlled axial compression at the column top, with increasing imposed strain levels from 0 up to 4%. The XX configuration exhibits slightly higher strain values, indicating enhanced energy dissipation and deformation capacity.

Fig 14 Total strain fields for the 1S, X, and XX configurations at a longitudinal strain of 3.3 %.

Fig 15 Plastic strain fields for the 1S, X, and XX configurations at a longitudinal strain of 3.3 %.

Fig 16 Evolution of maximum plastic spiral strains with imposed longitudinal column strain for single, crossed, and twin-crossed spiral reinforcements.

4 CONCLUDING REMARKS

The numerical investigations presented in this study highlight the significant influence of spiral reinforcement configuration on the mechanical behaviour of high-performance concrete columns. The use of the RICRAG model within the CAST3M framework has allowed for a detailed assessment of both elastoplastic and damage-driven responses, enabling a direct comparison with available numerical and experimental works.

During the elastic phase, the simulations confirm that all three configurations (1S, X, and XX) exhibit similar initial stiffness, with the confinement forces and tensile forces in the spirals concentrated predominantly at the column extremities. The reduced spiral pitch in these regions leads to greater confinement efficiency. Although increasing the number of spirals reduces the individual confinement force in each spiral, the overall confinement capacity of the column is improved due to the cumulative effect of multiple overlapping spirals.

In the post-yield phase, the comparative analysis of stress–strain curves for the 50S10, 50X10, and 50XX10 configurations reveals that the introduction

of crossed spirals enhances both the load-bearing capacity and ductility of the column.

The damage field analysis shows that damage initiates within the concrete cover zone at mid-height and subsequently propagates towards the core and column ends. This progression is accompanied by a redistribution of confinement forces from a uniform distribution at low strains to a bell-shaped distribution at higher strains, with peak forces concentrated at mid-height. The tensile forces in the spirals exhibit a similar evolution, confirming the correlation between spiral deformation and concrete damage. The strain analysis further shows that total and plastic spiral strains are maximal at mid-height. The XX configuration exhibits slightly higher strain values, suggesting enhanced energy dissipation and deformation capacity.

In summary, the present study demonstrate that crossed spirals, particularly the XX configuration, provide superior confinement efficiency, higher ultimate load capacity, and improved ductility. These benefits are attributed to the delayed rupture of spirals, more stress redistribution, and greater cumulative confinement provided by multiple crossing spirals.

Future research should expand these numerical investigations to combined loading scenarios, such as compression–bending and compression–torsion, and evaluate the seismic performance of multi-spiral configurations. The methodology developed in this work can also be applied to optimise spiral geometry, pitch distribution, with the aim of improving structural performance while maintaining constructability.

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6 NOTATION

The following symbols are used in this paper:

σ = the Cauchy stress tensor;

ε = the small strain tensor

H = the fourth-order Hooke elasticity tensor

Y = the local energy release rate

Y^{nl} = the nonlocal energy release rate

W = the weighting function

l_c = the characteristic length

Y_0 = the threshold value of the energy release rate

A_{Dir} = the brittleness parameter in tension

A_{Ind} = the brittleness parameter in compression

H = the Heaviside function.

$\langle \rangle_+$ = denotes the positive part of the tensor.

S_m = the pitch at mid-height

S_e = the pitch at the extremities, denoted S_e

E_s = the Young’s moduli of steel

ν_c = the Poisson’s ratios for concrete

ν_s = the Poisson’s ratios for steel

f_{c28} = the compressive strength of concrete at 28 days

f_{yh} = the yield strength of the spiral reinforcement

\emptyset_{sp} = the spiral bar diameter

F_t = the tensile strength,

γ_1 = the first kinematic hardening moduli

α_0 = the second kinematic hardening moduli